

Research on Parallel JFNK SP₃ Nodal Method for Pin-by-Pin Transport Calculation

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ABSTRACT

Pin-by-pin transport code plays a vital role in the study of next-generation reactor physics analysis codes. It can address the design requirements of different advanced and complex reactor core types, as well as the economic and safety demands of conventional pressurized water reactors. Improving computational efficiency is an issue to be addressed before pin-by-pin methods can be widely applied in nuclear engineering. This study applies the Jacobian-Free Newton-Krylov (JFNK) method and Red-Black domain-decomposition parallelization to a pin-by-pin code based on the SP₃ nodal method. The approach offers a potential solution to the computational-efficiency limitation. The developed code was validated using LWR pool problem, KUCA benchmark, and VERA core-physics benchmark to assess acceleration performance. Numerical tests indicate that the acceleration techniques enhance computational efficiency while maintaining eigenvalue accuracy comparable to the unaccelerated code. The developed pin-by-pin code is a good candidate for future engineering applications.

Keywords: pin-by-pin, JFNK, SP₃, parallel

1. INTRODUCTION

Three-dimensional pin-by-pin transport calculation based on the cell homogenization is an important way to implement the next generation neutronics analysis method. Considering that diffusion calculation applies many approximations and ordinary transport calculation methods (e.g., method of characteristics (MOC) or discrete ordinates method (S_N)) usually take more computing resources, simplified P₃ (SP₃) method is a compromise choice for engineering practice for whole core pin-by-pin transport calculation[1]. This study developed a program for pin by pin transport calculation using the nodal expansion method based on the SP₃ theory. The parallel computing function was implemented using the Red-Black domain decomposition method. The JFNK framework was integrate into the SP₃ nodal method in order to improve the numerical efficiency. Numerical results show that these acceleration methods improve computational efficiency, with minimal differences in results compared to the unaccelerated code.

2. THEORETICAL MODEL

2.1. Multigroup SP₃ Nodal Expansion Method

The multigroup SP₃ neutron transport equations are written as:

$$-D_{0,g} \nabla^2 \tilde{\phi}_{0,g} + \Sigma_{r0,g} \tilde{\phi}_{0,g} - 2\Sigma_{r0,g} \tilde{\phi}_{2,g} = \tilde{Q}_g, \quad (1a)$$

$$-D_{2,g} \nabla^2 \tilde{\phi}_{2,g} - \frac{2}{5} \Sigma_{r0,g} \tilde{\phi}_{0,g} + \Sigma_{r2,g} \tilde{\phi}_{2,g} = -\frac{2}{5} \tilde{Q}_g. \quad (1b)$$

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The neutron source \tilde{Q}_g is assumed to be isotropic.

$$\tilde{Q}_g = \sum_{g'=0, g' \neq g}^{g'=G} \Sigma_{s, g' \rightarrow g} \Phi_{g'} + \frac{\chi_g}{k_{\text{eff}}} \sum_{g'=0}^{g'=G} \nu \Sigma_{f, g'} \Phi_{g'}, \quad (2)$$

where $\Phi_{g'}$ is scalar flux and $\Phi_{g'} = \tilde{\phi}_{0, g'} - 2\tilde{\phi}_{2, g'}$; $\tilde{\phi}_{0, g}$ and $\tilde{\phi}_{2, g}$ are the 0th and 2nd order flux; $\Sigma_{r0, g} = \Sigma_{t, g} - \Sigma_{s, g}$, $\Sigma_{r2, g} = \Sigma_{t, g} + 4\Sigma_{r0, g}/5$, $D_{0, g} = 1/(3\Sigma_{t, g})$, $D_{2, g} = 9/(35\Sigma_{t, g})$, and $\Sigma_{t, g}$ is the total cross section; $\Sigma_{s, g}$ is the scattering cross section; χ_g is the fission spectrum; k_{eff} is the effective multiplication factor; $\nu\Sigma_{f, g}$ is the neutron generation cross section; g and g' are the neutron energy group number while G is the total number of energy groups.

In order to obtain the boundary condition expressions, we first need to get the expressions of the neutron partial currents. The partial current expressions of the SP₃ theory in direction u are,

$$j_0^\pm = \frac{1}{4}\tilde{\phi}_0 - \frac{3}{16}\tilde{\phi}_2 \mp \frac{1}{2}D_0 \frac{\partial \tilde{\phi}_0}{\partial u}, \quad (3a)$$

$$j_2^\pm = -\frac{1}{16}\tilde{\phi}_0 + \frac{7}{16}\tilde{\phi}_2 \mp \frac{5}{6}D_2 \frac{\partial \tilde{\phi}_2}{\partial u}. \quad (3b)$$

Omitting the energy group index, to numerically solve the above equation, the neutron flux and total source are approximated as follows:

$$\tilde{\phi}_n(\vec{r}) = \sum_{u=x, y, z} [A_{nu} \cosh(k_n u) + B_{nu} \sinh(k_n u)] + p_n(\vec{r}), \quad n = 0/2, \quad (4a)$$

$$p_n(\vec{r}) = a_{n,0} + \sum_{u=x, y, z} \sum_{m=1}^{m=2} a_{n,m}^u P_m \left(\frac{2u}{\Delta u} \right), \quad n = 0/2, \quad (4b)$$

$$\Phi(\vec{r}) = \phi_0 + \sum_{u=x, y, z} \sum_{m=1}^{m=2} \phi_m^u P_m \left(\frac{2u}{\Delta u} \right), \quad (4c)$$

$$Q(\vec{r}) = q_0 + \sum_{u=x, y, z} \sum_{m=1}^{m=2} q_m^u P_m \left(\frac{2u}{\Delta u} \right), \quad (4d)$$

where $k_n = \sqrt{\Sigma_{rn}/D_n}$; P_m are Legendre polynomials; A_{nu} , B_{nu} , $a_{n,0}$, $a_{n,m}^u$, q_0 , q_m^u are undetermined coefficient. Define the following vectors:

$$\vec{j}_{12}^{\text{in}} = \left(j_{0,x-}^+, j_{0,x+}^-, j_{0,y-}^+, j_{0,y+}^-, j_{0,z-}^+, j_{0,z+}^-, j_{2,x-}^+, j_{2,x+}^-, j_{2,y-}^+, j_{2,y+}^-, j_{2,z-}^+, j_{2,z+}^- \right)^T, \quad (5a)$$

$$\vec{j}_{12}^{\text{out}} = \left(j_{0,x-}^-, j_{0,x+}^+, j_{0,y-}^-, j_{0,y+}^+, j_{0,z-}^-, j_{0,z+}^+, j_{2,x-}^-, j_{2,x+}^+, j_{2,y-}^-, j_{2,y+}^+, j_{2,z-}^-, j_{2,z+}^+ \right)^T, \quad (5b)$$

$$\vec{\Phi}_7 = \left(\phi_0, \phi_1^x, \phi_2^x, \phi_1^y, \phi_2^y, \phi_1^z, \phi_2^z \right)^T, \quad (5c)$$

$$\vec{q}_7 = \left(q_0, q_1^x, q_2^x, q_1^y, q_2^y, q_1^z, q_2^z \right)^T. \quad (5d)$$

The following nodal response matrix of single energy group can be obtained[2, 3]:

$$\vec{j}_{12}^{\text{out}} = \mathbf{P}_{12 \times 12} \vec{j}_{12}^{\text{in}} + \mathbf{Q}_{12 \times 7} \vec{q}_7, \quad (6a)$$

$$\vec{\Phi}_7 = \mathbf{R}_{7 \times 12} \vec{j}_{12}^{\text{in}} + \mathbf{T}_{7 \times 7} \vec{q}_7. \quad (6b)$$

The discretized multigroup SP₃ equation and boundary conditions can be written as:

$$\mathbf{E} \cdot \vec{\varphi} = \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}} \mathbf{F} \cdot \vec{\varphi}, \quad (7a)$$

$$\vec{\varphi} = (\vec{\varphi}_1, \vec{\varphi}_2, \dots, \vec{\varphi}_G)^T, \quad (7b)$$

$$\vec{\varphi}_g = \left(\vec{j}_{12,g}^{\text{in}}, \vec{j}_{12,g}^{\text{out}}, \vec{\Phi}_{7,g}, \vec{q}_{7,g} \right)^T. \quad (7c)$$

Assume $\vec{X} = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{\varphi} \\ k_{\text{eff}} \end{pmatrix}$, then the residual equation can be obtained:

$$\vec{R}(\vec{X}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E} \cdot \vec{\varphi} - \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}} \mathbf{F} \cdot \vec{\varphi} \\ k_{\text{eff}}^{l-1} - k_{\text{eff}}^l \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

2.2. Variable Selection of Residual Functions Under Red-Black Iteration

In fact, to improve the computational efficiency and convergence rate of JFNK iteration, the number of residual functions $\vec{R}(\vec{X})$ and variables \vec{X} should be reduced to as small as possible. Therefore, we hope that as many variables of \vec{X} as possible can be eliminated by the algebraic or equivalent transformation method[4].

As shown in Figure 1, select the subset \vec{X}_{JFNK} of \vec{X} as the simplified independent variable:

$$\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}} = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{\varphi}_{\text{JFNK}} \\ k_{\text{eff}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (9a)$$

$$\vec{\varphi}_{\text{JFNK}} = (\vec{\varphi}_{1,\text{JFNK}}, \vec{\varphi}_{2,\text{JFNK}}, \dots, \vec{\varphi}_{G,\text{JFNK}})^T, \quad (9b)$$

$$\vec{\varphi}_{g,\text{JFNK}} = \left(\vec{j}_{\text{red},g}^{\text{in}}, \vec{j}_{\text{BC},g}^{\text{in}}, \vec{q}_{7,g} \right)^T, \quad (9c)$$

where $\vec{j}_{\text{red},g}^{\text{in}}$ is the inflow partial current vector of red nodes; $\vec{j}_{\text{BC},g}^{\text{in}}$ is the inflow partial current vector on the boundary of black nodes; $\vec{q}_{7,g}$ is the expansion coefficient vector of the nodal total source.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of \vec{X}_{JFNK} selection.

According to Eqs. (6a) and (6b), and the fact that outflow partial current of the red node is equal to the inflow partial current of the adjacent black node, \vec{X} can be uniquely determined by \vec{X}_{JFNK} after one

external source iteration calculation. Therefore, the residual equation in formula (8) can be rewritten as:

$$\vec{R}_{\text{JFNK}} \left(\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}} \right) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}' \cdot \vec{\varphi}_{\text{JFNK}} - \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}} \mathbf{F}' \cdot \vec{\varphi}_{\text{JFNK}} \\ k_{\text{eff}}^{l-1} - k_{\text{eff}}^l \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

The efficient preconditioner of Krylov methods is needed to ensure the good convergence rate and high efficiency of JFNK SP₃ nodal transport code. According to Zhou's work[4], the following physics-based preconditioner is adopted:

$$P^{-1} \vec{R}_{\text{JFNK}} \left(\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{\text{input}} \right) = \vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{\text{input}} - \vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{\text{output}}. \quad (11)$$

When $\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{\text{input}}$ introduces a very small increment $\epsilon \vec{v}$, there are:

$$P^{-1} \vec{R}_{\text{JFNK}} \left(\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{\text{input}} + \epsilon \vec{v} \right) = \vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{\text{input}} + \epsilon \vec{v} - \vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{\text{output}, \epsilon}, \quad (12)$$

where $\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{\text{output}}$ and $\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{\text{output}, \epsilon}$ are the output solutions using the source iterative framework of the SP₃ nodal transport code for the input solutions $\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{\text{input}}$ and $\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{\text{input}} + \epsilon \vec{v}$ respectively.

JFNK adopts the finite difference of the residuals $P^{-1} \vec{R}_{\text{JFNK}} \left(\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{\text{input}} \right)$ to skillfully approximate the Jacobian matrix-vector product due to the fact that Krylov methods need only the Jacobian matrix-vector product rather than Jacobian matrix, that is:

$$P^{-1} J \left(\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{\text{input}} \right) \vec{v} \approx \frac{P^{-1} \vec{R}_{\text{JFNK}} \left(\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{\text{input}} + \epsilon \vec{v} \right) - P^{-1} \vec{R}_{\text{JFNK}} \left(\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{\text{input}} \right)}{\epsilon} = \vec{v} - \frac{\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{\text{output}, \epsilon} - \vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{\text{output}}}{\epsilon}. \quad (13)$$

2.3. Iteration Strategy and Flowchart

For JFNK methods, the perturbation parameter ϵ in Eqs. (12) and (13) has a great influence on the accuracy of the Jacobian-free technology. In this work the following ϵ was chosen:

$$\epsilon = \frac{\sqrt{\left(1 + \left\| \vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^m \right\|_2\right) \epsilon_{\text{mach}}}}{\left\| \vec{v}_m \right\|_2}, \quad (14)$$

where m is the number of linear Krylov iterations. For double precision real numbers, ϵ_{mach} generally takes 10^{-6} .

To ensure both the computational efficiency and convergence rate of JFNK SP₃ nodal method, the convergence criterion of linear Krylov iterations can be adaptively chosen on the basis of the Newton residuals by using the Eisenstat-Walker forcing term η_m [5].

$$\left\| J \left(\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^m \right) \cdot \delta \vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^m + \vec{R}_{\text{JFNK}} \left(\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^m \right) \right\|_2 \leq \eta_m \left\| \vec{R}_{\text{JFNK}} \left(\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^m \right) \right\|_2, \quad (15)$$

$$\eta_m = \frac{\left| \left\| \vec{R}_{\text{JFNK}} \left(\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^m \right) \right\|_2 - \left\| J \left(\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{m-1} \right) \cdot \delta \vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{m-1} + \vec{R}_{\text{JFNK}} \left(\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{m-1} \right) \right\|_2 \right|}{\left\| \vec{R}_{\text{JFNK}} \left(\vec{X}_{\text{JFNK}}^{m-1} \right) \right\|_2}. \quad (16)$$

Since the residual evaluations of the SP₃ nodal method with physics-based preconditioner are fully based on the framework of the original source iteration, the JFNK SP₃ nodal transport code can present the higher efficiency only when the number of residual evaluations is less than the number of source iterations. In this work the GMRES (Generalized Minimal RESidual) method are chosen to solve the linear equations.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, the program was tested with LWR pool problem[6], KUCA(Kyoto University Critical Assembly) benchmark[7] and the VERA core physics benchmark[8]. To test the program function discussed above, four calculation options are set: SP₃, parallel SP₃, JFNK and parallel JFNK. In SP₃ option, the JFNK function is turned off and programs runs on one CPU, the convergence criterion on iteration is determined by eigenvalue and fission source, $|k_{i+1} - k_i| < 1 \times 10^{-6}$ and $|q_{F_{i+1}} - q_{F_i}| < 1 \times 10^{-4}$. In JFNK option, the JFNK function is turned on and programs runs on one CPU, the convergence criterion on iteration is determined by residual $F(x)$, which $|F(x_k)| < 1 \times 10^{-6} |F(x_0)|$. In parallel SP₃ or JFNK option, the JFNK function is turned off or on and programs runs on multiple CPU, the convergence criterion is same as serial option. In every benchmark, the eigenvalue results, iteration numbers and calculation times under different calculation option have been compared.

3.1. LWR Pool Problem

The 2D LWR pool problem consists of two different fuel cells and two different absorber cells surrounded by reflector, the boundaries of which are all vacuum. The geometry is shown in Figure 2 and the cross sections of materials are list in Table I.

Figure 2. The geometry of LWR pool problem.

Table I. Cross sections of materials in LWR pool problem.

Material	Σ_t (cm ⁻¹)	Σ_s (cm ⁻¹)	$\nu\Sigma_f$ (cm ⁻¹)
1	0.60	0.53	0.079
2	0.48	0.20	0.000
3	0.70	0.66	0.043
4	0.65	0.50	0.000
5	0.90	0.89	0.000

The cell is divided into fine meshes when calculating, where fuel cells and absorber cells are divided into 5cm × 5cm meshes and the reflector is divided into 6cm × 6cm meshes. The CPU numbers used in parallel options is 4. Using program with four options, the results are listed in Table II. The results show that JFNK method greatly decrease the iteration numbers and calculation times without changed

eigenvalue. Parallel method persist eigenvalue and iteration numbers. It greatly decrease the calculation times in SP_3 case, but has slight effect on JFNK case. The difference is caused by the communication between CPU in parallelization in JFNK case is much more than that in SP_3 case. So the time reduced by parallel calculation is a bit bigger than the time used in communication of parallel CPU when calculation.

Table II. Results of LWR pool problem.

Option	Eigenvalue	Iteration numbers	Calculation times (sec.)
SP_3	1.01007	1486	0.153
Parallel SP_3	1.01007	1486	0.089
JFNK	1.01007	123	0.042
Parallel JFNK	1.01007	123	0.037

3.2. KUCA Benchmark

Program has been tested by KUCA benchmark case 1: the small LWR case with control rod inserted. The geometry of KUCA Benchmark is shown in Figure 3 and the cross sections of materials are list in Table III.

Figure 3. The geometry of KUCA benchmark.

All cells are divided into $1\text{cm} \times 1\text{cm} \times 1\text{cm}$ meshes when calculating. The CPU numbers used in parallel options is 4. Using program with four options, the results are listed in Table IV. The results show that JFNK method greatly decrease the iteration numbers and calculation times without changed eigenvalue. Parallel method persist eigenvalue and iteration numbers. It greatly decrease the calculation times in SP_3 case and JFNK case.

3.3. VERA Core Physics Benchmark

Program has been tested by the VERA core physics benchmark. All cells are divided into $1\text{cm} \times 1\text{cm}$ meshes when calculating. Because serial options spend lengthy time on calculation, only parallel op-

Table III. Cross sections of materials in KUCA benchmark.

Region	Energy group	Σ_t (cm ⁻¹)	$\nu\Sigma_f$ (cm ⁻¹)	$\Sigma_{s,g \rightarrow 1}$ (cm ⁻¹)	$\Sigma_{s,g \rightarrow 2}$ (cm ⁻¹)
Core	1	2.23775×10^{-1}	9.09319×10^{-3}	1.92423×10^{-1}	2.28253×10^{-2}
	2	1.03864	2.90183×10^{-1}	0.00000	8.80439×10^{-1}
Control Rod	1	8.52325×10^{-1}	0.00000	6.77241×10^{-2}	6.45461×10^{-5}
	2	2.17460×10^{-1}	0.00000	0.00000	3.52358×10^{-2}
Reflector	1	2.50367×10^{-1}	0.00000	1.93446×10^{-1}	5.65042×10^{-2}
	2	1.64482	0.00000	0.00000	1.62452

Table IV. Results of KUCA benchmark.

Option	Eigenvalue	Iteration numbers	Calculation times (sec.)
SP ₃	0.96075	244	6.140
Parallel SP ₃	0.96075	244	1.209
JFNK	0.96075	123	4.881
Parallel JFNK	0.96075	123	1.104

tions calculation has been done and the CPU numbers used in parallel options is 90 and 200. The inner flux scan in JFNK option is setted to 7 for a better iteration speed. Using program with parallel options, the results are listed in Table V. The results show that JFNK method greatly decrease the iteration numbers and calculation times with a slight changed on the eigenvalue. Parallel method persist eigenvalue and iteration numbers. It greatly decrease the calculation times in SP₃ case and JFNK case.

Table V. Results of KUCA benchmark.

Option	Eigenvalue	Iteration numbers	Calculation times (sec.)
Parallel SP ₃ 90 CPUs	1.06409	9347	2071.307
Parallel SP ₃ 200 CPUs	1.06409	9347	719.286
Parallel JFNK 90 CPUs	1.06421	966	228.916
Parallel JFNK 200 CPUs	1.06421	966	113.331

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study developed a program for pin by pin transport calculation using the nodal expansion method based on the SP₃ theory. The parallel computing function was implemented using the Red-Black domain decomposition method.

The numerical efficiency was significantly improved by integrating the JFNK framework into the SP₃ nodal method. Concurrently, the Red-Black domain decomposition method was employed to implement the parallel computing function. The JFNK method achieved substantial reductions in the number of iterations and the total calculation time across all tested benchmarks without affecting the eigenvalue. For instance, in the VERA benchmark, moving from Parallel SP₃ 90 CPUs to Parallel JFNK 200 CPUs

reduced the calculation time from 2071.307 seconds to 113.331 seconds.

Numerical results show that these acceleration methods improve computational efficiency, with minimal differences in results compared to the unaccelerated code. The developed pin-by-pin code is a good candidate for following engineering applications.

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